

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY AND THE HISTORY OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. This article focuses on organic chemistry and the history of its development. During the article, the activities of scientists who contributed to this science are thoroughly studied and analyzed. Reasonable opinions and comments are given throughout the article.

Key words: organic chemistry, scientists, chemistry, organic dyes, organic substances.

ОРГАНИЧЕСКАЯ ХИМИЯ И ИСТОРИЯ ЕЕ РАЗВИТИЯ

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена вопросам органической химии и истории ее развития. В ходе статьи тщательно изучается и анализируется деятельность ученых, внесших вклад в эту науку. На протяжении всей статьи даются обоснованные мнения и комментарии.

Ключевые слова: органическая химия, учёные, химия, органические красители, органические вещества.

Organic substances have been known to people since ancient times, they knew how to make organic dyes (alizarin, purple, indigo), ferment grape juice to make vinegar, extract sugar and oil from plants, boil fats with alkalis to make soap, and this used substances. But for a long time, organic substances were used in the form of mixtures. By the 9th century, Arab alchemists were able to extract acetic acid from vinegar, and ethyl alcohol from musalas. In the 16th century, ethyl ether was obtained by treating ethyl alcohol with sulfuric acid. From the end of the 18th century to the beginning of the 19th century, obtaining organic substances in their pure form and studying them developed a lot, and it was considered that the name "organic chemistry" probably refers to the chemistry of substances that are part of plant and animal organs.

However, in 1824, the German chemist F. Völler synthesized oxalic acid from dicyanate, which is found in plant organs, and in 1828, he synthesized urea from ammonium cyanate in human and animal organs, and in 1845, German chemist A. V. Kolbe synthesized acetic acid. synthesis, in 1854 the French chemist M. Bertlot obtained oil, in 1861 the Russian scientist A. M. Butlerov obtained a sugary substance from common ant aldehyde, it was proved that organic substances are not found only in human and animal organs, and it is widely possible to obtain them by synthesis the way was opened. It has been proven that organic substances always contain the carbon element, and it was found that they contain hydrogen, oxygen, nitrogen and other elements in addition to the carbon element.

Thus, at the beginning of the 19th century, organic chemistry emerged as a science that teaches the chemistry of carbon compounds that make up organic substances. Organic chemistry is the main sources of organic substances - coal, oil, natural gas, fuel for the national economy through the processing of forest and agricultural products, paints, explosives, medicines. , supplies artificial i pak, fertilizer and other necessary products. The processing of cotton fiber, production of synthetic fibers, kapron, nylon and lavash is a major contribution to the development of the organic chemical textile industry.

The development of organic chemistry is a decisive factor in the development of technology and production in general. A. M. Butlerov (1828-1886) made a great contribution to

the development of organic chemistry with his book "Introduction to the complete study of organic chemistry" and the creation of the theory of the chemical structure of organic substances in 1861. Russian scientist N. N. Zinin (1812-1880) obtained aniline from benzene in industry, academician A. E. Favorsky (1860-1945) studied the chemistry of acetylene, allene and diene hydrocarbons, academician S. V. Lebedev obtained synthetic rubber in industry, academician N. D. Zelinsky (1861-1953) contributed to the development of organic chemistry with the chemistry of saturated and unsaturated cyclic compounds and methods of their synthesis.

Uzbek scientists have also made great contributions to the development of organic chemistry. Academician S. Y. Yunusov (1909-1995) conducted research on isoquinoline, erythrine, diterpene, quinoline, indole, quinazolidine, quinazoline, steroid, pyrrolizidine, pyridine, tropane and sulfur alkaloids. S. Y. Yunusov created the law of dynamic accumulation of alkaloids in various parts of plants, and together with his students, he isolated more than 800 alkaloids from medicinal plants growing in Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan, of which he determined the structural formula of 500 new ones. determined and brought the alkaloid chemistry of Uzbekistan to the leading position in the world. Among his students were N. K. Abubakirov, X. A. Abduazimov, F. Y. Yoldoshev, Z.F. Well-known chemists such as Ismailov, S. T. Akramov, R. N. Nuriddinov, M. S. Yunusov, S. I. Iskandarov have grown up. Academician O. S. Sodikov (1913-1987) is a world-renowned Uzbek chemist, scientist and organizational leader. His scientific works are devoted to the study of the chemistry of wild and cultivated plants and natural compounds growing in Central Asia. His students are famous chemists of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Armenia, Mongolia, Vietnam and Poland. From 1966 to 1983, O. S. Sodikov worked as the President of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. Academician I. T. Sukervanik (1901-1968) was a scientist who conducted consistent and extensive research in the field of "alkylation and acylation of aromatic compounds" and created a well-known school of organic chemists in this field. He also proved the process of anomalous alkylation, developed the mechanism of alkylation with alcohols, discovered a new reaction, and used the results of his research as defoliant and herbicide preparations in agriculture. Academician A. A. Abduvakhobov is a great scientist who created the element-organic school. Together with his students, he makes a great contribution to the chemistry of element-organic compounds, the problems of delicate organic synthesis, the determination of the chemical nature of the mechanism of action of molecular bioregulators at the molecular level, and the development of the science of organic chemistry in spatial chemistry. Under the leadership of A. A. Abduvakhobov, the first methods of synthesis of pheromone components were developed in the Central Asian region. The obtained substances are widely used to protect the cotton plant from harmful insects, remove insects with the help of attractants, grow cotton, and increase its productivity.

Academician M. A. Askarov is a scientist who has done great scientific work in the field of polymer chemistry and technology. His scientific works are aimed at polycondensation of aromatic diamines with aliphatic dibasic acids, in-depth and comprehensive study of polymerization reactions of new monomers, obtaining plastics containing nitrogen, oxygen and sulfur and improving their properties. He introduced works based on improving the properties of film-forming polymers under the influence of stabilizers obtained from oil industry waste to the production of polymer films and linoleums. Academician S. Sh. Rashidova is a scientist in the field of chemistry of high molecular compounds. His scientific research is devoted to the synthesis

of biologically active polymers with a known chemical structure, drugs based on polymers with versatile properties, the development of theoretical bases for the selection of plant protection agents and their application in practice. .

On the basis of these studies, a plasma substitute drug called "Kovilon" was obtained, the issues of encapsulation of seeds, rice and sunflower seeds with polymeric substances before sowing were studied based on the substance that controls plant growth - benzoyl formic acid. Scientific cooperation with French and Swedish scientists has been carried out.

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